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GUIDED READING PROGRAM IN KEY STAGE 2 LEARNERS AT STA. MARIA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

JENNALYN G. TORRES

TEACHER I

STA.MARIA ELEM.SCHOOL

TARLAC CITY, TARLAC, REGION 3, PHILIPPINES

ABSTRACT

Title: GUIDED READING PROGRAM IN KEY STAGE 2 LEARNERS AT STA.MARIA
ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

Name: Jennalyn G. Torres

Degree: Master of Arts in Education

Major in Guidance and Counseling

Institution: Osias Colleges, Inc.

The study employed the quasi-experimental research design in gathering data and information, using the pretest-posttest evaluation which allows immediate assessment of the intervention on guided reading. The participants of the study are the 26 learners from key stage 2 of Sta. Maria Elementary School, who are in the frustration level and non- decoders based on the pretest Phil IRI reading assessment. Oral reading passages were used as the research instruments for the pretest and posttests like the Great Runner, a text from the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil IRI) Manual.

It was revealed that there is an increase in the word recognition of the learners. There is a significant increase between the reading performance of the key stage 2 from pre -test to post test. The researcher has marked the following challenges encountered by the learners. Under the areas of word recognition, disregard punctuation ranked first as it was a committed error by the learners, followed by mispronunciation, lack of expression, refusal to pronounce and voice is hardly audible. An action plan was proposed to address the challenges. The school administration should support their teachers to equip themselves through trainings, seminars an workshops to enhance their knowledge for better implementation of Guided Reading Program.

Keywords: word recognition, Phil IRI, mispronunciation, lack of expressions

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INTRODUCTION

Reading is a basic skill that all students must possess in order to be successful. Reading is the foundation for future knowledge as students must be able to read in order to learn. With the variability of reading levels in classrooms, teachers are faced with students who are struggling to read (Reynolds, Wheldall & Madelaine, 2011).

Instilling a love of reading early gives a child a head start on expanding their vocabulary and building independence and self-confidence. It helps children learn to make sense not only of the world around them but also people, building social-emotional skills and of course, imagination.

As Cited by Ong (2016) The nature of the instruction provided in reading depends upon the types and purposes of reading in which children and adults engage (Gray, 1965). Gray suggests four major types and purposes of reading. The first type is reading with respect to the general form of reading, such as silent and oral reading. Second, reading level is determined by the reader's general attitude, such as "work-type" and "recreational." Third, reading is based on the specific purposes of the reader; for example, a child may read to find information relating to a problem or to follow detailed directions, and an adult may read to understand a situation better, or to determine validity of arguments relating to a social issue. Fourth, reading is based on the relation of the ideas involved, which is determined by facts and by relations inherent in the materials read. For instance, a child reads a geography text for the facts presented and interprets its content geographically.

Reading is a very good habit that one needs to develop in life. Good books can inform you, enlighten you and lead you in the right direction. There is no better companion than a start reading, you experience a whole new world. When you start loving the habit of reading you eventually get addicted to it. Reading develops language skills and vocabulary. Reading books is also a way to relax and reduce stress. It is important to read a good book at least for a few minutes each day to stretch the brain muscles for healthy functioning. Since reading is essential to learning, cultivating a love of reading children at a young age is the key to lifetime learning." When books are read aloud to children, they become a source of memorable, enjoyable, and stimulating formative experiences. Children who appreciate books are more inclined to read independently and are likely to do so for the rest of their life.

Galotti (2011) concurred that, during the elementary education from kindergarten to Grade 6, children learn basic literacy skills including learning to read and to write; later, they are expected to master content in subject areas as well as in higher grades. Learning to read involves stages in which early readers learn letters and sounds, and decoding skills in order to build confidence and fluency in reading both literacy and nonfictional text (Graves, 2006).

Guided reading is an essential part of any early literacy program. It involves placing students into small groups according to their reading ability and providing them with texts that are specifically chosen for their group, allowing them to read independently and individually. The goal is to build reading comprehension and fluency in a child's reading. Guided reading develops and uses the five essential elements of reading instruction: phonemic awareness, phonic skills, fluency in reading, vocabulary building, and text comprehension. It allows for explicit instruction in fluency and provides daily opportunities to expand vocabulary through reading, conversation, and explicit instruction.

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Guided reading is a small-group instructional approach where teachers support students in reading text at their instructional level to develop reading strategies and comprehension. Here are the key points about reading programs. The benefits of guided reading program are the following, accelerates literacy development by challenging students with appropriately leveled texts, allows for rich discussions about texts in a small group setting, encourage students to take risks and build confidence as readers and provides targeted, strategy-based instruction to strengthen reading skills. The components of a guided reading lesson are Before Reading, During Reading and After Reading. Before reading says that activate prior knowledge, introduce new vocabulary, and discuss the text. While in During Reading students read the text individually while the teacher provides support and guidance as needed. After reading discuss the meaning of the texts and make teaching points based on students' needs. (Scholastic Inc. 2020)

Learning to read is about listening and understanding as well as working out what's printed on the page. Through hearing stories, children are exposed to a wide range of words. This helps them build their own vocabulary and improve their understanding when they listen, which is vital as they start to read. It is important for them to understand how stories work too. Even if your child does not understand every word, they will hear new sounds, words and phrases which they can then try out, copying what they have heard. As children start to learn to read at school, you can play an important role in helping to keep them interested in books. Find out what interests them, help them to find books that will be engaging and fun, and spend time reading the books they bring home from school together. (Pearson, 2024)

Reading comprehension is one of the primary ways for a human to acquire knowledge, and the cultivation of reading skills in students by instructors to facilitate the distillation of knowledge remains one of the central tasks in literary education. To maximize the effects of reading comprehension, instructors have developed a lot of strategies and tools, including computer technology. Computer technology is a widely used vehicle to promote literacy of students in reading, as evidenced by a large number of studies that focused on the effects of intelligent tutoring system (ITS) in the age groups of children in grades 1–3 (Hauptmann et al., 1994), kindergarten (Voogt and McKenney, 2007), K-12 (from kindergarten to 12th grade) students (Proudfoot, 2016; Xu et al., 2019; Pahamzah et al., 2022), and adults (Ramachandran and Stottler, 2000). These ITS systems assisted readers by acting as coaches (Hauptmann et al., 1994), reading companions (Madhani et al., 2019), or using augmented reality (Voogt and McKenney, 2007) to build interactive digital environments. Artificial intelligence, including Bayesian networks and fuzzy logic, was used to adaptively support students in learning environments, which had shown positive results (Eryilmaz and Adabashi, 2020).

Carol Anne St. George, EdD, an associate professor and literacy expert at the University of Rochester's Warner School of Education, wants kids to fall in love with reading. "It helps grow their vocabulary and their understanding about the world," she says. The closeness of snuggling up with a favorite book leads to an increase in self-confidence and imagination, and helps children gain a wealth of knowledge from the books you share. And it only takes 15 minutes a day of reading together to nurture this growth.

Reading exposes us to other styles, other voices, other forms, and other genres of writing. Importantly, it exposes us to writing that is better than our own and helps us to

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improve,” says author and writing teacher, Roz Morris. “Reading—the good and the bad—inspires you.” Not only that, but reading is a critical foundation for developing logic and problem-solving skills.

Reading gets your mind working across different areas. For starters, it involves comprehension to process the words you read. Beyond that, you can use your analytical abilities, stimulate memories, and even broaden your imagination by reading words off a page. When you read a lot, you undoubtedly learn a lot. The more you read, you can make it to the level of being considered “well-read.” This tends to mean that you know a little (or a lot) about a lot. Having a diverse set of knowledge will make you a more engaging conversationalist and can empower you to speak to more people from different backgrounds and experiences because you can connect based on shared information. Some people may argue that “ignorance is bliss,” but the truth is “knowledge is power.” And, the more you read, the more you get to know! That’s why you can bet that any educational degree you choose to obtain will involve some forms of reading. (University of the People 2019)

According to Frank Serafini “There is no such thing as a child who hates to read. They are only children who have not found the right book “Stimulating activities like reading are scientifically proven to prevent mental decline. throughout your life.

Research by Robert S. Wilson found that those who read books throughout their life have a 32% lower decrease in mental abilities as they get older.

The simple view of reading states that both word decoding and linguistic comprehension are vital to reading comprehension. According to the construction- integration model, comprehension is the result of two core processes, namely, construction and integration. The former process activates the information from the text and prior knowledge that resides in the memory of the reader, and the latter process spreads the activation throughout this network until activation settles (Butterfuss et al., 2020)

Reading fluency is reading with speed, accuracy, and appropriate expression Fluency is considered one of the critical components of reading and a target area within the Common Core State Standards. Fluency instruction is typically provided in the elementary grades because literacy instruction aims to develop students’ basic word reading skills and automatic word recognition to support reading comprehension. (National Reading Panel, 2000).

Literacy instruction in the secondary grades increasingly focuses on reading comprehension and content acquisition. Starting in sixth grade, reading fluency is no longer a curriculum standard for typical readers, who are expected to read and comprehend grade- level texts with proficiency (National Governors Association Center for Best Practices & Council of Chief State School Officers, 2010).

A large number of students enter the secondary school grades with deficits in reading performance, showing difficulties in comprehension, automatic word recognition, decoding, and fluency (Manset-Williamson & Nelson, 2005). In a large study ($N = 1,025$) of struggling readers in sixth through eighth grades, students exhibited difficulties in decoding, reading fluency, and comprehension (Cirino et al., 2013). In particular, 46% of the struggling readers demonstrated

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difficulties in reading fluency, and 84% demonstrated difficulties in comprehension. Overall, 78% of the sample had overlapping difficulties in both areas (Cirino et al., 2013).

In spite of the fact that reading fluency is not included in the instructional standards for secondary grades, fluent and accurate word reading has been theorized to facilitate reading comprehension (LaBerge & Samuels, 1974; Perfetti, 1980, 1985). Students with slow and labored word recognition expend mental energy trying to decode the text, which detracts from the task of comprehending (Rasinski, 2003). The reader's cognitive load may be taxed at the expense of efficient comprehension processing (Oakhill et al., 2003; Perfetti, 1985). When students recognize words rapidly and with ease, cognitive resources can be spent on inferring meaning from text (LaBerge & Samuels, 1974; Perfetti, 1980). Students' word reading proficiency is highly predictive of reading comprehension in the younger grades (García & Cain, 2014). There is some evidence to suggest that a shift occurs around age 10, at which point students' word reading becomes less predictive of reading comprehension for older readers (García & Cain, 2014). The caveat to this finding is that reading fluency may still be an important and necessary component of reading instruction for older struggling readers as these students continue to struggle with fluent and accurate word reading. Furthermore, inadequate reading fluency has implications for older struggling readers who are expected to learn grade-level content by reading text.

Struggling readers in the secondary grades need support to increase fundamental literacy skills such as fluency (Kamil et al., 2008). The majority of struggling readers in the secondary grades require interventions that support several components of reading (e.g., reading fluency, word reading skills, comprehension; Cirino et al., 2013). Given the importance of reading fluency to free up cognitive resources to focus on comprehension and thus content learning, it is necessary to determine the impact of reading fluency interventions on the reading fluency and reading comprehension outcomes of secondary struggling readers and to identify the features of those interventions that best remediate the reading fluency and comprehension needs of struggling readers.

Tony Stead provides wonderful ways to enhance children's understanding and engagement when reading for information. He outlines practical approaches to ensure all children can become confident and competent readers of nonfiction. Part one examines effective ways to teach children how to extract the information that is explicitly stated in a text. Covered are strategies such as using prior knowledge, retelling, locating specific information, and the role of nonfiction read-aloud. Part two explores interpreting information, including making connections between the text, the reader, and the outside world, making inferences and revising inferences based on reflection. Part three looks at evaluating information, assisting children in developing critical reading skills, differentiating fact from opinion, locating author bias, and identifying techniques writers use to persuade readers' thinking. Part four offers an array of practical ways to reinforce and extend children's nonfiction reading skills, including working with visual information such as maps and diagrams. It also provides pre and post-assessment strategies, procedures for monitoring progress, curriculum planning ideas, and instruction on guided reading.

According to Jim Trelease, author of the best-seller, *The Read-Aloud Handbook*: "Every time we read to a child, we're sending a 'pleasure' message to the child's brain. You could even call it a commercial, conditioning the child to associate books and print with pleasure".

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Developing a connection between “pleasure” and reading is crucial. Learning is the minimum requirement for success in every field of life.

At the most basic level reading is the recognition of words. From simple recognition of the individual letters and how these letters form a particular word, to what each word means – not just on an individual level, but also as part of a text. In English, as in many other languages, different combinations of the same letters can be used to form different words with completely different meanings. So, the letters *t c a a* can make both *cat* (an animal that goes meow) and *act* (which has a number of meanings, from ‘do something’, to ‘behave in certain ways’, to ‘perform in a play or film’). Recognition of the actual word is not enough on its own to constitute reading. Understanding what we are reading is key and is certainly the main point of teaching reading in a class. It’s not much good if our students simply stare at a text and say, ‘Well, I don’t understand it, but it looks nice!’ However, understanding a text is quite a complex issue and something that we will try and examine in the rest of this article.

Reading requires you to have the patience to build a cognitive perspective. This is considered to be a prime brain-stimulating activity to sharpen your mind. Individuals engaged in reading have a slower memory decline than those who avoid reading. It also improves memory and builds focus. Having a strong vocabulary can readily benefit you to strengthen your writing ability both personally and professionally. It inspires writers to stay positive and express their thoughts more clearly. Reading helps us in developing a knack for understanding the perspective of different authors that helps in writing about things by ourselves. It is very crucial to comprehend the subject matter and allow our memory to retain it. (Leverage Edu 2021)

The Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS) 2021 survey revealed insights into reading outcomes of 4th graders in 57 countries and territories, showing that some countries experienced improvements while others faced declines in reading proficiency levels.

In England, nine and 10-year-olds ranked fourth in the world in a major international literacy study, with a slight improvement in ranking since the previous assessment. However, scores remained relatively stable despite disruptions to education due to the Covid pandemic. (Guardian Graphic 2021).

Reading performance in Cambodia has been a focus of various initiatives aimed at improving literacy outcomes among students. Studies have shown that providing high-quality storybooks and reading support can effectively enhance reading abilities, especially for children from disadvantaged backgrounds. In Cambodia, efforts to promote a culture of reading have included teacher professional development, materials and development, school-based management and leadership, caregiver and community engagement, and the use of technology to support early-grade reading outcomes. (Crawford Micheal et.al, May 19, 2023)

According to the OECD’s PISA 2022 assessment, on average, 15-year-olds in Cambodia score 329 points in reading, which is lower compared to an average of 476 points in OECD countries. Baseline assessments of upper preschool and grade 1 student performance in pre-literacy and early grade reading revealed lower-than- expected levels of oral language ability and pre-literacy skills among students in Cambodia. Room to Read Cambodia has also been actively involved

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in improving literacy and girls' education in the country as part of the efforts to enhance the quality education in Cambodia. Bank.Org.2023)

In Singapore Students Continued to Demonstrate Strong Reading Literacy Skills. Despite the COVID-19 pandemic's widespread disruptions to learning and life globally, Singapore improved its reading literacy scores from PIRLS 2016 (mean score of 576) to

2021 (mean score of 587). This also makes Singapore the only education system where students have made steady progress over the past 20 years since the PIRLS study was first administered in 2001. Singapore's performance may be due to factors such as the refinements made to our English Language teaching and learning curriculum over the past two decades, the programmes in place to help students who need additional literacy support, and the efforts made by schools and teachers to ensure students could continue learning effectively throughout the COVID-19 pandemic. (Ministry of Education Singapore, May 16,2023)

The Department of Education (DepEd) said that the Philippines' poor performance in the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) indicates a five- to six- year lag in learning competencies in the country. The Philippines ranked 77th out of 81 countries globally in the student.

According to the OECD, each 20-point deficit from the average signifies a one- year lag in the annual learning pace of 15-year-olds in PISA-participating countries. DepEd Undersecretary for Curriculum and Teaching Gina Gonong believed that the PISA result for the Philippines remains "positive" and acknowledged that many OECD countries experienced a decline in performance due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Senate chairman on basic education Sherwin Gatchalian said the government should intensify learning recovery programs to address pandemic-related learning loss and ensure that learners have access to well-designed remediation plans.

The implementation of the K-12 Basic Education Program HAMON: BAWAT BATA BUMABASA, the Department of Education (DepEd) is continuously fulfilling its mandate to produce productive and responsible citizens equipped with essential

competencies and skills for lifelong learning. To make every learner a proficient reader, schools across the country are tasked to help learners.

In Cebu, there is a significant concern regarding the reading proficiency of grade 3 students in Central Visayas. According to report by DepEd, approximately 75% of Grade 3 students in Central Visayas struggle with reading or have low reading comprehension. Salustiano Jimenez, regional director of the Department of Education-Central Visayas (DepEd-7), observed that the reading ability of the learners in Grade 1 is at par with that of those who are in Grades 2 and 3, citing the "negative impact of the coronavirus disease (Covid-19) pandemic. As mentioned, (it was) because of the pandemic, two years that they didn't have contacts. They rely on modules. In reading, teachers are really need to interact with the learners. During the pandemic, he said learners did not have enough teachers to supervise reading sessions, as lessons were being relied to the parents and guardians who do not have the skills to teach reading and comprehension. Jimenez cited that the programs of Vice President and DepEd

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Secretary Sara Duterte like the special remedial classes to pupils who need special attention in reading and comprehension as well as the National Learning Camp, a fun-filled activity that focuses on reading especially to K-1 to K-3 stages can help the learners. (Saavedra, John Rey 2023)

Tarlac City is no exception for that matter because there are also struggling readers. The Tarlac City Schools Division, develop the Project Recovery and Engagement of Struggling readers through Curriculum Updates and Explicit Instruction (RESCUE). The utilization is done during the remediation/enrichment classes. Project Rescue is incorporated in class program allotted for reading remediations. These classes are not optional but mandatory as a support for school's learning recovery and continuity plans. The learners can only proceed to the next skill or strategy if he /she already satisfied the requisite skills. Specifically, for non- decoder, a learner cannot proceed to letter sound knowledge if he has not mastered yet the letter name knowledge. Same with the non- comprehenders. Meanwhile, if the learner is observed to be having difficulties still in noting details, he/she shall not proceed to the next one. Numerically, if the learner already attained 50% or more in the last activity for that specific reading strategy (non-comprehends), he/she is now entitled to proceed to the next strategy.

In support to the Project Recovery and Engagement of Struggling readers through Curriculum Updates and Explicit Instruction (RESCUE) of Tarlac City Schools Division and responding actively to DepEd memorandum No.173s.2019 on Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3B's Initiative) the Sta. Maria Elementary School initiated the Guided Reading Program in Key Stage 2 learners to focus more on the learners who need further attention especially the non-readers and frustrated readers. Based on the pretest result of PHI- IRI Key Stage 2 learners in Sta. Maria Elementary School, 33 or 38.82% out of 85 learners are independent, 26 or 30.58%, are instructional, 22 or 25.89% are frustrated and 4 or 4.70% are non-decoders. And through the rigid observation of the teachers, it is evident that learners of Sta. Maria Elementary School have reading difficulties, especially with word recognition. The difficulty of the learners in word recognition should be given priority. Before comprehension and understanding will take place, children must first learn how to properly enunciate word/s and be familiar with their meaning is the first step before the full context could be decoded.

The teaching staff foresee that such intervention can increase the performance of the learners with reading difficulty. This can help them to improve and cope-up with the activities inside the classroom that involve reading skills. This way their confidence will be boosted by giving them more opportunities to participate more actively in class.

Statement of the Problem

1. How is the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners described before the Implementation of Guided Reading Program?
2. How is the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners described after the Implementation of Guided Reading Program?
3. Is there a significant increase between the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners before and after the Implementation of Guided Reading Program?
4. What are the challenges encountered in Implementation of Guided Reading Program?

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5. What plan of action can be proposed to address the challenges?

Null Hypothesis

There is significant increase in Reading Performance of the Key Stage 2 learners after the Implementation of Guided Reading Program.

Theoretical Framework

Guided reading is informed by Vygotsky's (1978) Zone of Proximal Development and Bruner's (1986) notion of scaffolding, informed by Vygotsky's research. The practice of guided reading is based on the belief that the optimal learning for a reader occurs when they are assisted by an educator, or expert 'other', to read and understand a text with clear but limited guidance. Guided reading allows students to practice and consolidate effective reading strategies. Vygotsky was particularly interested in the way's children were challenged and extended in their learning by adults. He argued that the most successful learning occurs when children are guided by adults towards learning things that they could not attempt on their own.

Key Stage 2 learners of Sta. Maria Elementary School, Tarlac City that reading proficiency relates to one of the important aspects of learning and knowledge. In the first part, the study presented the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners before and after the Implementation of Guided Reading Program. The challenges encountered in Guided Reading Program were identified. On the last part of the study a plan of action was proposed to improve the Implementation of Guided Reading Program in key stage 2.

Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

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METHODS

Research Design

This research utilized a quasi-experimental research design in gathering data and information. According to Thomas (2020) the quasi-experimental design aims to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between an independent and dependent variable. This kind of method is most likely to be conducted in fields settings in which random assignment is difficult or impossible. The design is concerned with the pretest/posttest design, which involves collecting information only on program participants.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Sta. Maria Elementary School located in Barangay Santa Maria, Tarlac City. There are 197 learners from kindergarten to grade six. This school is headed by a Head Teacher III, Dr. Velvet C. Alva, with eight teachers, one Administrative Officer and one job order or utility.

Barangay Santa Maria already existed even before the Pre-Spanish period. According to the oral accounts of its earliest settlers, its pioneering residents came from the Ilocos Region particularly in Sta. Maria, Ilocos Sur. Prior to the progress of the barangay, it was formerly a forested area with thick grassland. The first school in barrio Santa Maria was established in the year 1948 with Mr. Tomas Manalo as the first public school teacher.

Research Participants

The participants of the study were the 26 learners from key stage 2 of Sta. Maria Elementary School, who are in the frustration level and non-decoders based on the pretest Phil IRI reading assessment. Out of the 85 learners from grade four to six, there are 22 in the frustration level and 4 non-decoders, 8 are in grade four, 9 in grade five and 5 in grade. Only in grade five that their non-decoders.

Research Instruments

The data-gathering instrument used in this study were the following.

- A. Oral reading passages used for the pretest and posttest, and it was graded during the assessment. The Great Runner, a text from the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil IRI) Manual, was used for the post-test.
- B. Individual Reading Inventory, includes information on their oral reading proficiency as well as the errors they made in word recognition in both tests. For every grade passage,

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the word error marking method was adhered to. To provide an overview of the learners' oral reading proficiency, these separate inventories were combined.

C. Big books, printed activity sheets, flash cards, a list of spelling terms, and video lessons

Data Gathering Procedure

The Guided Reading Program in Key Stage 2 Learners, was conducted within six (6) weeks by the reading teacher as shown below.

Week	Lesson	Approach /Activity
Week 1 Phonemic Awareness	Letter names and sounds with letter recognition.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Singing a song Title: Alphabet Phonic Song ➤ Phoneme Isolation: Learners identify Individual phonemes in words, e.g. "What is the first sound in 'boat'?" (/b/) ➤ Answer the activity sheet on letter names and recognition ➤ Giving Feedback/Follow Up
Week 2 Phonics	Consonant Vowel Consonant Pattern	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Singing a song Title: Everybody's Reading Now ➤ CVC Phonics Song ➤ Use Flash cards with CVC Pattern ➤ Answer the activity sheet on CC Pattern ➤ Giving Feedback /Follow Up
Week 3 Phonics	Consonant Vowel Consonant-Consonant Pattern	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Singing a song Title: CCVC Words Phonics Phase 4 ➤ Use Flash cards with CVCC Pattern ➤ Spelling Bee ➤ Answer the activity sheets on CVCC Pattern ➤ Giving Feedback/Follow Up

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Week 4 Fluency	Basic Sight Words	<ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Practice Reading Title: Let's Read! Sight Words Sentences! I, Like my Practice Reading English➤ Guess the word: Learners write down a set of 5 words, then place them in the middle of the table. The teacher or nominated learner then has to pick a word and give clues (e.g. "it ends with -ig")➤ Answer the activity sheets on basic sight words➤ Giving Feedback/Follow Up
Week 5 Fluency Vocabulary	Simple Words and Sentences.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Choral reading: Read a short text aloud, and then have them read it aloud in unison.➤ Teacher modeling: regularly reading aloud to students serves as a model for reading fluency. Be expressive and vary your pace so that students get a sense of the flow. If possible, have students read along with their own copy of the text, so they can link it to the words they hear aloud.➤ Read the activity sheets on simple words and sentences.➤ Giving Feedback/Follow Up

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Week 6 Comprehension	Short Stories	<ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Practice Reading➤ Paired reading: Having children read aloud to one another encourages them to develop the expression and flow needed for fluency. Pair students of different ability levels for more powerful learning, but make sure the disparity is not too great.➤ Questioning: Follow up reading time with open-ended questions that prompt students to think deeply about the text. For example, if reading a narrative, you might ask students how a character changed over the course of a story, or how a central problem influenced the action.➤ Giving Feedback/Follow Up
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Data Analysis

The study used frequency counts and percentages to facilitate the test of significant increase on the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners between before and after the implementation of the Guided Reading Program.

$$\text{Percentage \%} = \frac{\text{Frequency}}{\text{Total Population}} \times 100$$

Phil IRI Reading Profile

Phil IRI Oral Reading Criteria

Oral Reading Level	Word Reading Score (in%)
Independent	97-100%
Instructional	90-96%
Frustration	89% and below
Non-Decoder	wasn't able to decode letters/ words

In the analysis of Word Reading level of each learner, the researcher used the Phil- IRI reading test criteria wherein the percentage of word recognition accuracy to be under Independent level is 97-100% (0-4 errors) 90-96% (5-12 errors) for a learner to be under Instructional level, and a percentage of 89% and below (13 and above errors) will put a learner under frustration level, and wasn't able to decode (letters and words) will be under Non-decoder, these learner displayed refusal to read.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This selection discusses the results on guided reading program of key stage 2 learners. Data gathered from the respondents were subjected to statistical analysis and the results were interpreted. Data are shown in tables and figures followed by textual interpretations.

Reading Performance of Learners Before the Implementation of Guided Reading Program

The Key Stage 2 Learners who come from grades 4 to 6 have a total of 85 learners in Sta. Maria Elementary School. Their reading performance was determined through a pretest using the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil IRI). The results revealed that 22 belong to the frustration level and 4 are non-decoders. These 26 learners were given priority in this study on Guided Reading to equip them with word recognition skills. The rest of the learners are independent and instructional who could already read with comprehension.

Table 1. Reading Performance of Learners (Pretest)

Indicator	Frequency	Percentage
Frustration	22	84.62
Non-Decoder	4	15.38
Total	26	100

Table 1 shows the data on struggling readers in Sta. Maria Elementary School, Tarlac City. The data is so alarming that the researcher conceived of a Guided Reading Program and conducted it within six (6) weeks.

Reading Performance of Learners After the Implementation of Guided Reading Program

Having a posttest is important for observing the reading development of a child because it allows for the assessment of progress and improvement over time. The posttest provides a comparison to the pretest, allowing educators to measure the effectiveness of interventions and instructional strategies implemented during the learning process. It helps identify the areas where the child may still be struggling and provides valuable information for targeted remedial instruction.

Additionally, the posttest can reveal common reading miscues and highlight areas that need further attention and support. By conducting post-tests, educators can track the development of reading skills longitudinally and monitor the growth of reading prosody, expressivity, phrasing, smoothness, and rate. Overall, post-tests play a crucial role in understanding the progress and needs of individual students, informing instructional decisions,

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and ensuring that appropriate interventions are provided to support their reading development. (Burns, Julianne 2024)

Table 2. Reading Performance of Learners (Posttest)

Indicator	Frequency	Percentage
Independent	1	3.85
Instructional	10	38.46
Frustration	15	57.69
Non-Decoder	0	0
Total	26	100

Table 2 shows the data in posttest reading results of the key stage 2 learners in Sta. Maria Elementary School. There are twenty-six learners who participated in the study. On the span of six (6) weeks the learners show improvement in their reading ability

The following data are the results, under independent level, 1 learner or 3.85% of the total learners, while in the Instructional level 10 learners or 38.46%, then in the frustration level is 15 learners or 57.69%. Zero or no learner belongs to the non-decoder

Difference in the Reading Performance of the learners before and after the Guided Reading Program

The researcher used frequency counts and percentages. To facilitate the significant increase on the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners, before and after the Guided Reading Program.

Table 3. Reading Performance of the learners before and after the Guided

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Reading Program

Indicator	Before		After	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Independent	0	0	1	3.85
Instructional	0	0	10	38.46
Frustration	22	84.62	15	57.69
Non-Decoder	4	15.38	0	0
Total	26	100	26	100

Table 3, shows that there is a significant increase in the performance of the key stage 2 learners of Sta. Maria Elementary School, Tarlac City. Before the Guided Reading Program, no learner belongs to Independent level likewise in the Instructional. It is a good sign that after the implementation of the Guided Reading Program.

There is an improvement or increase in the number of learners under the frustration level there are 22 learners before the implementation of the program but after the implementation it decreases to 15 learners. There is no non-decoder anymore after the implementation of the program which is obviously a positive impact of the Guided Reading Program.

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Table 4. Summary of Pretest and Posttest Reading Performance of the Key stage 2 Learners

Name of Learner	Grade Level	PRETEST Reading Level	POSTTEST Reading Level	Increase/Decrease
Matt Harvie	Grade IV	Frustration	Instructional	Increase
Vhic Slater	Grade IV	Frustration	Frustration	Increase
Richard	Grade IV	Frustration	Frustration	Increase
Edgardo	Grade IV	Frustration	Frustration	Increase
Christian	Grade IV	Frustration	Frustration	Increase
Noah	Grade IV	Frustration	Frustration	Increase
Kristille	Grade IV	Frustration	Frustration	Increase
Jessa May	Grade IV	Frustration	Frustration	Increase
Prince Kean	Grade V	Frustration	Instructional	Increase
Andrew	Grade V	Frustration	Frustration	Increase
Mark Anthony	Grade V	Non-Decoder	Frustration	Increase
Jhon Michael	Grade V	Non-Decoder	Frustration	Increase
John Jhaymes	Grade V	Frustration	Frustration	Increase
Prince Ronnie	Grade V	Frustration	Instructional	Increase
Kenneth	Grade V	Non-Decoder	Frustration	Increase
Wencel Marck	Grade V	Frustration	Frustration	Increase
Raphael	Grade V	Non-Decoder	Frustration	Increase
Justine	Grade V	Frustration	Frustration	Increase
Chairyl Shaine	Grade V	Frustration	Instructional	Increase
Ruby Mae	Grade V	Frustration	Instructional	Increase
Jennylyn	Grade V	Frustration	Independent	Increase
Dave	Grade VI	Frustration	Instructional	Increase
Jayson Vien	Grade VI	Frustration	Instructional	Increase
Dennis	Grade VI	Frustration	Instructional	Increase
Sarah	Grade VI	Frustration	Instructional	Increase
Roselyn	Grade VI	Frustration	Instructional	Increase

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Table 4 shows the summary of pretest and posttest results of the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners. The Pretest performance of grade four learners from 8 frustration level decrease to 7 after the Posttest reading assessment. While in the grade five learners in the pretest 9 are under frustration, in the post test decrease them in 4 learners, then 4 learners became Instructional and 1 learner became independent in the posttest. All of the grade 6 learners improved after the implementation of the program. From being under frustration level during the pretest to instructional level after the posttest. This only shows that given the proper attention and utilizing a program that well suit their needs, the pupils well show a significant in improvement in their performance.

Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of the Guided Reading Program

The researcher encountered several challenges throughout the implementation, guided reading program, and here the followings.

Table 5. Challenges encountered in the Implementation of Guided Reading

Challenges Encountered	Frequency	Rank
Mispronunciation	12	2
Refusal to Pronounce	9	4
Disregard punctuation	15	1
Lacks of Expression	10	3
Voice is hardly audible	8	5

Table 5 shows that learners facing reading difficulties encountered various challenges. Disregard punctuation ranked first committed error by the learners, followed by mispronunciation, lack of expression, refusal to pronounce and voice is hardly audible.

All 15 learners out of 26 encountered disregards of punctuation, these learners are continuing without stopping or pausing in the period or commas. They felt that if they read without pausing or stop in the period they understand or comprehend what they read. I said to them that look at the right punctuation so they feel what are they reading.

The error in mispronunciation are committed due to incorrect decoding. Some words are not familiar to them or not easily to pronounce it, for example the word *became* they read it *become*. Another word is *there* they said it *three*. Also, the word *goddess* they pronounce it *goodess*. In the error of lacks of expression, learners read in a monotonous tone. They not know if they need to express their feelings if happy or sad what are they reading.

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In the error due to refusal to pronounce, the learner was unable to read because of lack of knowledge in phonemes and not familiar to the words, examples are *Hippomenes*, *great*, *married* and *race*. And some learners voice is hardly audible voices, because of their weak voice and some are very shy to express their thoughts. They need to practice more in reading to boost their voice quality.

These challenges that have risen led to the proposal of action plan.

Proposed Action Plan to address the Challenges encountered in the Implementation of Guided Reading Program

The foregoing is the proposed action plan to address the challenges met by the researcher as the reading teacher in the implementation of Guided Reading Program.

Areas of Concern	Activity	Strategy	Means of Verification
Disregard punctuation	Read aloud to focus on punctuation marks	Introduce the different punctuation marks Be familiar to the punctuation marks Teach the correct use of punctuation	Photos list of Short Stories
Mispronunciation	Oral Reading Drills	Look up unfamiliar words Practice 10 unfamiliar words everyday	Photos list of Flashcards
Lacks of Expression	Listen and repeat the words	Use video lesson to show the right expression Read and record	Copy of Video Lesson
Refusal to Pronounce	Rereading Practice reading and record	Phoneme Isolation, Blending, Alliteration and Segmentation	Photos of Phrases and Sentences
Voice is hardly audible	Paired reading Choral Reading	Vocal Exercises to improve pitch, breathing and enunciation Practice reading aloud from a book or any kind of reading materials. Record yourself to review your speaking later and find areas you can improve	Copy of Audio Lesson

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CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section presents the conclusion derived from the results of the study and the recommendations of the researcher based on the results

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The reading performance of the key stage 2 learners before the Implementation of the Guided Reading Program there are under Frustration level and Non- decoders.
2. After the Implementation of the Guided Reading Program the reading performance of the learners improved. From 1 independent learner, under instructional level it becomes 10, frustration level it becomes 15 and there is no more learner under the non-decoder.
3. There is a significant increase between the reading performance of the key stage 2 learners before and after the Implementation of Guided Reading Program. There are no more non-decoders and most of the learners improved from frustration level to instructional level.
4. The following are the challenges encountered by the learners. First is Disregard punctuation mark, next is mispronunciation, then lack of expression, next, refusal to pronounce and last voice is hardly audible.
5. Action Plan is proposed.

Recommendations

1. Based on the forgoing findings and conclusions, the researcher recommends the following.
2. Use the Phoneme Isolation, Blending, Alliteration and Segmentation to improve the word recognition of the learners. So, before the reading assessment done, they know how to read. Use the different activities used in the Guided Reading Program as show there is an improvement in the reading performance of the learners after the implementation.
3. Adapt the Guided Reading Program to improve the performance of the learners
4. Use different activities like Singing a song using the video lessons, and instructional materials, phonemes isolation, using flashcards, spelling bee, paired reading and choral reading.
5. Implement the proposed action plan.

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